

Impact of Fuel Temperature Distribution on Reactor Core Simulations

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ABSTRACT

A novel methodology is proposed to enhance the accuracy of multi-physics calculations in nuclear reactor analysis based on a high-fidelity modeling of the fuel temperature in the reactor core, with the aim of achieving a more realistic representation of reactor operating conditions and improving the reliability of safety assessments. Unlike traditional models that employ a single, representative fuel temperature for each fuel pin, the proposed method explicitly considers the temperature distribution within the fuel pellet. By incorporating the local temperature profile into the generation of homogenized nuclear data, the method allows for a more accurate treatment of the self-shielding effect and a better understanding of how the intra-pellet temperature shape affects resonance broadening and neutron interaction probabilities (Doppler effect) in different fuel regions. The results obtained demonstrate a clear deviation between the traditional single-temperature model and the distributed-temperature approach, both in terms of homogenized cross-section calculations and power distribution. These findings demonstrate the importance of explicitly modeling fuel temperature distributions to achieve more precise and physically consistent reactor simulations, therefore improving reactor safety and performance analyses.

1. INTRODUCTION

Doppler and self-shielding effects provide essential negative reactivity feedback by linking fuel temperature variations to resonance absorption. Since these important physical phenomena depend on the local temperature distribution, an accurate modeling on the latter is vital for reliable power and safety predictions during power transients. This work introduces an improved numerical approach that explicitly considers the radial temperature profile within the fuel, enhancing the consistency of Doppler and self-shielding evaluations in reactor multi-physics simulations. The importance of improved temperature modelization of fission reactor cores is further underscored by the 2022 establishment of the Task Force on Fuel Temperature Assumptions in Depletion Analyses [OECD/NEA, 2022].

Traditional reactor physics tools generally rely on transport/diffusion theory and follow a three-step calculation approach: neutron-nuclide cross section process, infinite lattice calculation and reactor calculation. In the conventional methodology, the homogenization process assumes a single, effective fuel temperature for the entire fuel assembly, representative of its overall state. In the new proposed approach, a single representative fuel temperature is no longer used, but instead a temperature distribution within the fuel pin is considered both in the homogenization procedure and the nodal code. This addition has led to an increase in the descriptive parameters of the homogenized cross sections, moving from a predefined number of parameters to a variable number depending on the temperature points within the fuel. Accordingly, several modifications have been introduced into a nodal code in order to accommodate these additions.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2 is introduced the calculation tools used in this study, describe the modification introduced in the codes in order to implement the new modeling of the temperature of fuel pins, and present the reactor benchmark used to verify the validity of the proposed approach. Section 3 presents the results obtained in different core scenarios, while the last section is devoted to summary and conclusions.

2. NEUTRONIC CODES

The neutron codes used for the implementation of the new approach are Serpent2 [1], as Monte Carlo code for calculation of homogenized cross sections, and the nodal code NEM [2].

While in Serpent it is straightforward to consider a radial temperature distribution within the fuel pin to obtain the correct homogenized cross-section, a rather extensive modification had to be introduced in the NEM nodal code to enable a consistent treatment of temperature-dependent cross sections. The upgraded code is now able to handle a variable number of temperature points within the fuel pin, and includes a multidimensional interpolation scheme within the Nemtab data structure [2].

To make the comparison between the conventional and the new approach, the C5G7 reactor benchmark was taken into consideration [3]. The core is composed by sixteen fuel assemblies, eight uranium oxide (UO₂) assemblies and eight mixed oxide (MOX) assemblies, surrounded by a water reflector. The Hot Zero Power condition were considered, where the fuel, moderator and clad all have a temperature of 551K. The core has been radially numbered, as shown in Fig. 1, to represent 3D and 2D power distributions.

13	14	15	16
9	10	11	12
5	6	7	8
1	2	3	4

Figure 1. Radial numbering of the C5G7 core.

The effective fuel temperature, defined as a weighted fuel temperature, is 551K while the central fuel temperature is 1000K. Having this data available, the surface temperature was obtained using the definition of effective fuel temperature, so it was possible to evaluate all the different temperature distribution. For comparison between single-temperature and multi-point temperature cases, the effective fuel temperature is evaluated using the linear Finneman approximation [4].

$$\bar{T}_{effective} = 0.3 \cdot T_{centerline} + 0.7 \cdot T_{surface} \quad (1)$$

In the present work is neglected the coupling with thermal-hydraulic calculations, as the scope is limited to the verification of the validity of the new approach independent from the self-consistency required for real reactor studies. A further simplification consists in the adoption of the same temperature distribution in all fuel pins within a given assembly. This latter assumption maintains computational efficiency while preserving the essential physical effects of intra-pellet temperature variations, offering a more accurate Doppler feedback representation than the conventional single-temperature approach.

To test this new approach based on a more accurate modeling of the fuel pin temperature, is considered the following three temperature distribution:

- The parabolic ($\alpha=2$) and cubic ($\alpha=3$) distributions, with the first representing a typical behaviour during normal operational condition and the second representing also conditions that can arise during accidents, featuring a similar profile with a temperature at the pellet boundary that remains lower than the parabolic distribution for a large portion of the pellet.

$$T(r) = T_{surface} + (T_{centerline} - T_{surface}) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{r^\alpha}{R^\alpha}\right) \quad (2)$$

- The peaked distribution, simulating scenarios that may occur during certain accidental conditions, characterized by a significantly higher temperature at the center of the pellet maintaining a lower temperature at the boundaries for a substantial section of the pellet.

$$T(r) = T_{centerline} \cdot e^{-\frac{r}{\Delta R}} \quad (4)$$

The temperature distribution inside a fuel pin described by the three different cases are shown in Fig. 2, considering 5 and 10 radial temperature points. All the considered temperature distributions share the same effective, central, and surface temperatures; only the radial shape of the temperature profile varies. However, in the plotted results the surface (and thus effective) temperatures appear slightly different. This apparent discrepancy arises because, in the radial discretization of the fuel pin, each region is assigned an area-averaged temperature. Consequently, the temperature of the outermost zone—representing the surface—differs slightly among the various distributions due to this averaging process.

Figure 2. Surface-averaged temperature distributions inside the fuel pin

3. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

In this section are presented the results of a series of simulations adopting the upgraded code and the three radial fuel temperatures described above, focusing on the comparison with the conventional results based on a single temperature. The analysis is carried out in terms of differences in the homogenized cross sections generated by the Monte Carlo code—specifically the total, fission, and capture cross sections—for both UO_2 and MOX fuel assemblies. The impact of the temperature distribution on the power distribution calculated by the nodal code is examined, including three-dimensional, two-dimensional, and one-dimensional representations. This comprehensive analysis aims to assess the influence of the intra-pellet temperature profile on neutronic parameters and power prediction accuracy. Statistical error propagation was performed on the homogenized cross-section variations—following the law of propagation of uncertainty as defined in the GUM [2, Eq. (10)]—to account for the intrinsic fluctuations of the Monte Carlo method, ensuring a reliable quantification of the observed differences.

3.1. Parabolic Temperature Distribution

The differences obtained in the homogenized cross sections (7 energy groups) between the single temperature case and the five temperature points parabolic distribution case is presented in Fig. 3. It is found that the percentage variations observed are more pronounced for the UO_2 assembly compared to the MOX one.

Figure 3. Differences between single-temperature and 5-temperatures-parabolic in MOX (left) and UO₂ (right) fuel assemblies homogenized cross sections.

This behavior arises from the stronger Doppler contribution in uranium-based fuel, mainly due to the dense resonance structure of U²³⁸ across the epithermal range. In MOX fuel, the lower U²³⁸ content and higher plutonium fraction reduce this effect, as isotopes like Pu²⁴⁰ exhibit only a few narrow resonances (notably around 1 eV). Additionally, the harder neutron spectrum of MOX and its weaker self-shielding further limit the impact of Doppler broadening.

The comparison between 5- and 10-point parabolic temperature cases presented in Fig. 4 (MOX on left and UO₂ on right) shows nearly identical homogenized cross sections at high energies, with differences emerging below 0.625 eV. This reflects the stronger Doppler and self-shielding effects in the resonance region, where the many U²³⁸ absorption peaks make the cross sections more sensitive to finer temperature discretization.

Figure 4. Differences between 5-10 temperatures parabolic in MOX(left) and UO₂(right) fuel assemblies.

In MOX fuel (Fig. 4, left), slightly larger low-energy deviations appear because the various plutonium isotopes have distinct resonance behaviors that reduce this compensation (Fig. 5). Nevertheless, the differences between the 5- and 10-point parabolic cases remain below 0.5%, confirming that the 5-temperature distribution provides sufficient accuracy with lower computational cost.

For the UO₂ assembly, total cross section variations are minimal across all energies, as shown in Fig. 5, due to compensation among capture, fission, and scattering components, which balance each other and keep the total nearly constant. This compensation is demonstrated by the fact that the relative difference in the total cross section does not match the sum of the relative differences of its individual components.

Figure 5. Relative error in the total cross sections for UO₂ (left) and MOX (right) fuel assembly.

The power distributions obtained with 5 and 10 parabolic temperature points are nearly identical in all representations (3D, 2D, and 1D). Fig. 6 relative to the 3D core power shows that, although the 10-point case offers a finer temperature description, the 5-point distribution already captures the intra-pellet gradient accurately, confirming its adequacy for power calculations. When comparing 3D power distributions obtained with single-temperature and 5-point parabolic cross sections, the more pronounced deviations occur at the lateral nodes, while both central and corner nodes show smaller differences, although such differences almost always remain greater than 1%. This trend reflects both the spatial flux behavior and the heterogeneous fuel composition. The lateral nodes correspond to MOX assemblies located at the UO_2 – MOX interface, where harder spectra and strong flux gradients enhance the sensitivity to temperature-dependent cross sections.

Figure 6. Differences in 3D power distributions, in the corner (left), lateral (cente) and central (right) nodes.

In contrast, the central nodes contain UO_2 fuel, characterized by a softer spectrum and stronger Doppler feedback, which tends to moderate local reactivity variations and results in smaller power deviations. Although the peak power appears at node 12, the maximum deviation occurs at node 15, where the flux remains high and radial gradients are strongest, enhancing the Doppler sensitivity. The deviation then slightly decreases as the flux diminishes toward the upper region. In contrast, central and corner nodes show their maximum deviation in the lower part of the core, where the more thermal spectrum causes the single-temperature case to underestimate absorption. Overall, the imposed parabolic intra-pellet temperature profile affects each region differently, depending on local flux, spectrum, and fuel composition.

Considering the 2D axially collapsed radial power map, the same qualitative behavior is observed, as shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. 2D axially collapsed radial power differences between single-temperature and 5-temperatures-parabolic.

The largest differences between the single-temperature and five-temperature parabolic cases occur at the lateral nodes, while the smallest deviations are found at the corner assemblies and intermediate ones at the central nodes. This confirms once again that the lateral regions are the most sensitive to the representation of the fuel temperature profile. These nodes correspond to MOX fuel assemblies, whose harder neutron spectrum and weaker Doppler feedback make the reactivity more sensitive to local temperature variations, amplifying the impact of cross-section changes on the nodal power. Conversely, the central and corner nodes contain UO_2 fuel, where the stronger Doppler effect and softer spectrum lead to greater self-regulation of reactivity, thus reducing the observed deviations in the collapsed power distribution.

Regarding the 1D radially collapsed power distribution, the axial trend of percentage deviations shows a gradual decrease from nodes 1 to 11, a minimum at node 12, a sharp rise at nodes 13–14, followed by a moderate decline up to node 21 and a slight increase near the top, as illustrated in Fig. 8. In the lower part of the core, the flux and spectrum are more thermal and regular, reducing sensitivity to intra-pellet temperature variations. The minimum at node 12 corresponds to the power peak, where reaction-channel compensation is strongest. The sudden rise at nodes 13–14 coincides with spacer-grid locations, where local perturbations in coolant flow and heat transfer modify temperature gradients and enhance Doppler-related effects. Above this region, the flux field becomes more stable, decreasing sensitivity, while near the top, lower flux and stronger leakage effects cause the deviations to increase again.

Figure 8. 1D radially collapsed axial power differences between single-temperature and 5-temperatures-parabolic.

3.2. Parabolic-Cubic-Peaked distributions

This section compares the single-temperature case with the parabolic, cubic, and peaked temperature distributions (five points each). Since parabolic and cubic profiles share a similar shape, their results are expected to be close. The observed differences depend strongly on the fuel type: MOX assemblies show smaller deviations than UO₂ due to the lower Doppler sensitivity and weaker self-shielding of plutonium isotopes.

The homogenized cross sections for the peaked temperature profile show distinct differences compared to the single-temperature case, unlike the more gradual parabolic and cubic profiles, as evidenced in Fig. 9. This discrepancy arises because the peaked distribution's sharp central maximum and steep radial decay alter the spatial weighting of resonance absorption, shifting the effective Doppler feedback toward the cooler pellet periphery.

Figure 9. Differences in capture cross sections for MOX (left) and UO₂ (right) fuel assemblies considering the parabolic, cubic and peaked temperatures distribution.

Among the various reaction types, the largest discrepancies are found in the homogenized capture cross section, represented in Fig. 9. This behavior is consistent with the fact that, in the resonance region, the capture cross section approximately follows a $1/\sqrt{T}$ dependence due to Doppler broadening. Consequently, any modification in the intra-pellet temperature distribution can significantly alter the effective averaged value of the capture cross section. In the MOX fuel assembly, the capture cross section exhibits its minimum deviation at about 4 eV for the 1–5 parabolic and 1–5 cubic comparisons,

while at the same energy the 1–5 peaked case shows the maximum deviation. This inversion can be explained by the higher sensitivity of plutonium isotopes — particularly Pu^{240} and Pu^{242} — to temperature asymmetries in that energy region, where their narrow resonances amplify the local Doppler effect. For the UO_2 fuel assembly, the largest difference in the capture cross section appears around 5.5×10^3 eV (energy group 2) for all three cases, corresponding to the main U^{238} resonance region. However, at 4 eV (energy group 3) the 1–5 peaked case shows the smallest absolute deviation, while the 1–5 parabolic and 1–5 cubic cases still exhibit values close to their respective maxima. This indicates that the peaked distribution tends to reduce the Doppler broadening at low energies, where the colder central regions of the fuel dominate the effective absorption behavior.

When comparing the nodal code results obtained using the homogenized cross sections corresponding to the single-temperature case, the parabolic (with 5 and 10 temperature points), the cubic (5 points), and the exponential peaked temperature distribution (5 points), the resulting k_{eff} values and the difference in terms of pcm compared to the single temperature case are as follows:

• Single temperature	$k_{\text{eff}} = 1.0315063$	
• Parabolic-5 temperatures	$k_{\text{eff}} = 1.0317995$	$\Delta = +29$ pcm
• Parabolic-10 temperatures	$k_{\text{eff}} = 1.0316312$	$\Delta = +12$ pcm
• Cubic-5 temperatures	$k_{\text{eff}} = 1.0300617$	$\Delta = -144$ pcm
• Peaked-5 temperatures	$k_{\text{eff}} = 1.0402195$	$\Delta = +871$ pcm

The results show that the parabolic cases (5 and 10 temperature points) yield nearly identical reactivity values, confirming that five temperature points are sufficient to capture the relevant physics, with the 10-point case providing only a marginal refinement. The cubic distribution results in the lowest reactivity, as its higher average temperatures in the intermediate radial region enhance Doppler broadening and resonance absorption. Conversely, the peaked (exponential) profile produces a markedly higher k_{eff} — about 842 pcm above the 5-point parabolic case — due to its steep central gradient and colder outer regions, where reduced Doppler broadening weakens resonance self-shielding. This substantial deviation, roughly equivalent to one dollar of reactivity, underscores the strong sensitivity of reactor neutronics to the assumed intra-pellet temperature distribution and the importance of using physically consistent temperature profiles in safety analyses.

Concerning the 3D nodal power distribution shown in Fig. 10, the overall behavior of the percentage differences remains consistent with what was previously observed: the largest deviations occur in the lateral nodes, while the central and corner nodes exhibit smaller discrepancies. This trend confirms that the lateral regions, characterized by high neutron flux gradients and strong spatial coupling, are the most sensitive to local variations in the Doppler-related cross sections. However, particular attention should be given to the 1–5 peaked case. Although it follows the same qualitative trend, the magnitude of the differences is noticeably more pronounced, as clearly shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Differences in 3D power distributions, in the corner (left), lateral (center) and central (left) nodes.

The steeper and more asymmetric nature of the peaked temperature distribution enhances the local reactivity variations across the axial direction, amplifying the effect of the intra-pellet temperature gradient on the power distribution. This results in a more accentuated deviation pattern compared to the parabolic and cubic cases, even though the overall shape of the profile remains similar.

When analyzing the 2D radially collapsed and 1D axially collapsed power distributions, the same general behavior described earlier is observed: the differences remain relatively small in the central nodes and increase toward the peripheral ones. However, a notable distinction emerges when comparing the different temperature distributions.

Figure 11. 2D axially collapsed radial power (right) and 1D radially collapsed axial power (left) differences between single-temperature and 5-temperatures-parabolic, cubic and peaked.

In the 1D collapsed distributions, the 1–peaked case consistently exhibits smaller deviations compared to the other cases, indicating that the exponential (peaked) temperature profile leads to a smoother spatial power response when the results are radially averaged. Conversely, the 1–cubic case shows the largest differences, suggesting that the stronger curvature of the cubic profile amplifies local variations. On the other hand, for the 2D axially collapsed distribution, the trend is inverted: as clearly shown in Figure 11, the 1–peaked case displays by far the largest percentage differences along the axial direction. This indicates that, although the exponential temperature distribution produces smoother results in the radial average, its strong asymmetry and steep gradient along the pellet radius enhance the axial power redistribution effects, resulting in a significantly higher axial sensitivity.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the impact of intra-pin fuel temperature distributions on reactor neutronics, focusing on Doppler and self-shielding effects. Using an upgraded version of the NEM nodal code which allows for non-uniform temperature distribution in the fuel pins and assemblies, it was found that the accounting for the radial temperature gradient leads to measurable variations in homogenized cross sections and nodal power. In particular for this case, differences between the 5- and 10-point parabolic cases were minimal, while the cubic profile yielded slightly lower reactivity. The exponential (peaked) distribution, however, produced a markedly higher k_{eff} — about 842 pcm above the 5-point parabolic case — highlighting the strong sensitivity to the temperature-field shape. Power deviations were largest in lateral nodes and smaller at central and corner ones. Overall, it can be concluded that even simplified radial temperature profiles enhance the physical accuracy of nodal calculations compared to the traditional single-temperature approach, leading to more precise and physically consistent reactor simulations which improve reactor safety and performance analyses. Future studies will include coupling with COBRA-TF and transient analyses to further assess the dynamic effects of intra-pellet temperature distributions.

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